

changed by varying its plant density. This has an important implication for achieving synchrony with *in situ* green manure crops. In practice, linear alternate plots of low and high plant densities in the field can produce green manure with contrasting quality. Green manure produced in this manner can be mixed and incorporated during land preparation to achieve better

synchrony between N release and demand in lowland rice.

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Low-cost management of iron toxicity in farmers' fields in Sierra Leone

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Iron (Fe) toxicity affects up to 60% of the total cultivable inland valley swamps (IVS) in West Africa and reduces grain yield by up to 80%. Resource-poor farmers cannot afford to use high-cost technologies such as chemical amendments to reduce Fe toxicity. Over the years, on-station experiments have shown the great potential of organic amendments and toxicity-tolerant rice genotypes to improve Fe-toxic soils in the IVS. However, their adaptability in farmers' fields with varying soil types, water regimes, and extent and severity of Fe toxicity needs to be evaluated.

Two types of trials (to determine the effects of variety and organic amendment) were conducted on Fe-toxic IVS at 12 sites in Sierra Leone in the 1995–96 and 1996–97 seasons. Farmer groups from four villages participated. The soil characteristics varied and were in these ranges: 3.8–5.3 for pH in water, 3.6–4.1 for pH in KCl, 0.07–0.35% N, 0.4–3.5 mg Bray-1 P kg⁻¹ soil, 7.2–13.2% organic C, 3.1–6.9% Fe₂O₃, 31–75% sand, 12–31% silt, and 11–38% clay.

The first-season trials were managed by both farmers and researchers, whereas the second-season trials were farmer-managed. In the first trials, two rice genotypes, one tolerant (ROK24) and one

susceptible (ROK5), were grown unreplicated with the farmers' variety in 120-m² plots. Four-week-old seedlings were transplanted at 0.15 × 0.2-m spacing. Only N as urea was applied uniformly at 10 kg ha⁻¹. Iron toxicity ratings were scored 7 wk after transplanting using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) developed at IRRI. Harvesting was done at physiological maturity; materials were sun-dried and weighed and the grain yield adjusted to 14% moisture content. The second trials involved three treatments with organic amendment (5t *Calopogonium mucunoides* ha⁻¹, 5t partially decomposed rice husk ha⁻¹, and the control [no amendment]) using the farmers' variety as the test variety. Urea was also applied at 10 kg N ha⁻¹ and data were collected with the same method used in the first trials.

The selected sites were acidic and had low available P and high Fe. Tolerant genotype ROK24 significantly outyielded susceptible genotype ROK5 (Table 1). The mean grain yield increase in ROK24 over that of susceptible ROK5 and the local check was 90.4% and 57.6%, respectively. Overall, yields were higher in the first season than in the second season, presumably because of differences in management.

Incorporation of 5 t ha⁻¹ partially decomposed rice husk or *C. mucunoides* increased grain yield over the control by 76% and 77%, respectively (Table 2). This proves the ameliorating power of organic residues to correct Fe toxicity. Higher grain yield corresponds to lower Fe toxicity scores and vice versa, indicating a strong negative association between severity of Fe

Table 1. Varietal differences in response to iron toxicity in farmers' fields over two seasons.^a

Variety	Effective tillers m ⁻² (no.)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)
ROK24 (tolerant)	95	1.5 (3)
ROK5 (susceptible)	53	0.8 (7)
Local	59	0.9 (5)
CV (%)	15.4	24
Variety	11	0.2
Site (replication)	***	***
Season (year)	**	**

^aNumbers in parentheses indicate Fe toxicity score by the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES). ** and *** = statistically significant at 1% and 0.1%, respectively.

toxicity and grain yield. Tiller production showed a trend similar to that of grain yield. Differences between cropping seasons were not significant.

In conclusion, tolerant genotype ROK24 manifested a great potential for use in iron-toxic IVS. Some local rice genotypes showed a moderate degree of tolerance for Fe toxicity. Application of 5 t ha⁻¹ of partially decomposed rice husk or *C. mucunoides* alleviates Fe toxicity and increases rice yield in farmers' fields with varying water and toxicity regimes.

Table 2. Effect of organic residue in alleviating grain yield reduction caused by iron toxicity in farmers' fields over two seasons.^a

Organic amendment	Effective tillers m ⁻² (no.)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)
Decomposed rice husk	74	1.4 (3)
<i>C. mucunoides</i>	77	1.4 (3)
Control	55	0.8 (5)
CV (%)	11.2	23.1
Organic amendment	9	0.3
Site (replication)	***	***
Season (year)	ns	ns

^aNumbers in parentheses indicate Fe toxicity score by SES. ns = not statistically significant. *** = significant at 0.1%.

Instructional videos available

The Leaf Color Chart (LCC) (8:20 min)

Farmers generally observe the color of rice leaves to determine a rice crop's need for nitrogen fertilizer. Dark green rice leaves mean a high nitrogen content, while pale green rice leaves necessitate the application of more nitrogen fertilizer.

Mere observation, however, holds no absolute guarantee in measurement accuracy. Thus, to better help farmers determine their rice crops' need for nitrogen, the leaf color chart (LCC) was developed.

The Leaf Color Chart (LCC) instructional video was produced to familiarize farmers and extension workers with the proper use of this new and affordable farming implement.

Portable chlorophyll meter for nitrogen management in rice (13:30 min)

In agriculture, excess nitrates can actually be highly damaging to crops and the environment. There is, thus, a need to efficiently manage the application of nitrogen fertilizers on rice crops.

The Portable Chlorophyll Meter for Nitrogen Management in Rice introduces the features and use of the chlorophyll or SPAD meter which is capable of measuring the relative nitrogen content in plant leaves through a simple, quick, and nondestructive procedure.

Go break into the code (13:30 min)

Genetic engineering need not be a property of the scientific few. This is what IRRI had in mind when it produced *Go break into the Code*: to make the general public grasp and understand the seemingly complicated science through a visually stunning, fast-paced, and entertaining presentation of the genetic code, DNA sequencing, and plant biotechnology.

The video also gives the public a glimpse as to how IRRI scientists are redesigning the rice plant—that most important food staple, using biotechnology tools.

These instructional videos are available in English, in the 3/4-inch u-matic and VHS formats, and in the NTSC, SECAM, or PAL systems.

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